

Current insights on cardiovascular and neurodegenerative relations of direct oral anticoagulants and their biotransformation

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Abstract

An intriguing connection explored over the years is the link between neurodegenerative diseases and thrombosis. A number of studies have focused on associations between cardiovascular events and neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, multiple sclerosis, and Huntington's. This evolving concept has led to numerous investigations of the role of coagulation factors and innate immune components in the pathogenesis of neurological diseases.

On the other hand, it is well known that for decades, vitamin K antagonists such as warfarin and acenocoumarol were the only oral anticoagulants available for treating and preventing deep vein thrombosis (DVT), pulmonary embolism (PE), and PE following hip or knee replacement surgeries. They were also used for stroke prevention and for reducing the risk of major cardiovascular events in patients with chronic coronary artery disease (CAD) or peripheral artery disease (PAD). However, the need for frequent international normalized ratio (INR) monitoring, clinic visits, and dietary restrictions posed barriers to the optimal use of vitamin K antagonists in real-world practice. The advent of non-vitamin K antagonists, also known as direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs), has provided an important alternative, and they are now recommended as preferred over warfarin or acenocoumarol whenever possible, based on clinical trial findings and real-world evidence for more than 14 years.

Thus, the objective of this review is to summarize the latest advancements in the therapeutic applications of DOACs and to present insights into their biotransformation and the impact of the CYP450 enzyme system on their metabolism.

Keywords

CYP2C19, DOACs, drug interactions

Introduction

The current population of patients with atrial fibrillation (AF), venous thromboembolism (VTE), and pulmonary embolism (PE) is significant. Globally, the burden of

AF remains substantial. In 2019, an estimated 59.7 million people were living with AF worldwide. The incidence and prevalence of AF continue to rise, highlighting the need for effective prevention and treatment strategies (Li et al. 2022; Pastori et al. 2023; Noubiap et al. 2024). For this population

of patients, the selection of the appropriate agent, dosage, and duration of treatment, especially in those with multiple comorbidities, may be considered a clinical challenge. To support healthcare professionals, guidelines have been issued, including the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) Guidelines for the management of AF (ESC Clinical Practice Guidelines) and the American Society of Hematology 2023 Guidelines for the management of VTE (Middel-dorp et al. 2023). Similar documents with good practices assist clinicians in assessing the benefits of anticoagulation against the potential risk of bleeding. Algorithms have been introduced to evaluate the risk of stroke, identify patients at high risk, and assess bleeding risk from identified factors for AF and stroke (Hindricks et al. 2021; Brundel et al. 2022).

VTE, which includes both deep vein thrombosis (DVT) and PE, is another significant global health issue. Annually, about 10 million cases are reported worldwide. The incidence of VTE is 1–2 cases per 1,000 individuals per year, with higher rates in Western countries and lower in Eastern regions. VTE is considered the third most common cardiovascular disease (CVD) globally (Data and Statistics on Venous Thromboembolism/Venous Thromboembolism (Blood Clots)/CDC 2024), following heart attack and stroke. Mortality rates are high, especially for untreated PE, which is fatal in 10–30% of cases (Pastori et al. 2023). The exact number of PE cases is not always clear, but it is estimated that many of the 900,000 VTE cases in the U.S. include PE (Middel-dorp et al. 2023; Data and Statistics on Venous Thromboembolism/Venous Thromboembolism (Blood Clots)/CDC 2024). These diseases are common and pose a serious health risk. To achieve the best possible outcomes, it is essential to apply effective therapeutic methods in the treatment of CVD (Vazquez 2018; Tublin et al. 2019; Fischer et al. 2023; Kuneš et al. 2023).

In recent decades, the relationship between neurodegenerative diseases (NDDs) and thrombosis has become a developing field of study. Although research has investigated this connection, it is confirmed that several cardiovascular risk factors (CVRFs)—including obesity, diabetes, hypertension, and high cholesterol—are also identified as risks for NDDs (Stampfer et al. 2006). Thrombosis also triggers a complex series of events, including inflammation, tissue ischemia, activation of platelets and immune cells, complement system activation, and the coagulation cascade. This interconnected network can create a destructive cycle that exacerbates the severity of the condition, potentially causing further damage to tissues and organs (Stark et al. 2021; Sun et al. 2022). Thrombosis plays a crucial role in the development of NDDs by obstructing both arterial and venous cerebral blood vessels, leading to tissue ischemia, cell death, and irreversible brain damage, ultimately resulting in neurodegeneration (Beura et al. 2023). As a key mediator of thrombosis, thrombin (Martin 2018; Petersen et al. 2018) can contribute to cerebrovascular and neuronal dysfunction in conditions such as Alzheimer's disease (van Oijen et al. 2005). Moreover, recent research has shown that fibrin can specifically aggregate with amyloid- β proteins (A β), leading to the formation of occlusive blood clots in cerebral vessels. These are associated with vascular and blood–brain barrier (BBB) dysfunction, ischemic and

hypoxic brain conditions, neuroinflammation, and neuronal death (Cortes-Canteli et al. 2010; Zamolodchikov et al. 2016; Cajamarca et al. 2020). Consequently, it can be postulated that anticoagulant therapy may offer significant advantages in the regulation and prevention of NDDs within therapeutic protocols and clinical management strategies.

DOACs, by targeting thrombin, have become an important part of the standard of care for various cardiovascular conditions (Chen et al. 2020), but their role in the management of NDDs is still being explored (Grossmann 2022) due to their potential benefits in NDDs. In this sense, DOACs are currently mostly applied in cardiovascular conditions.

While preclinical studies and observational research on AF patients suggest that DOACs may offer protective effects against dementia, including Alzheimer's disease (AD), clinical trials necessary for therapeutic approval have yet to be completed. DOACs act on pathological thrombin, an early indicator of AD, similar to toxic tau and amyloid- β (A β) proteins. Especially in hippocampal and neocortical areas, the release of parenchymal A β into the blood induces thrombin and pro-inflammatory bradykinin synthesis by activating factor XII of the contact system. Thrombin promotes platelet aggregation and catalyzes conversion of fibrinogen to fibrin, leading to degradation-resistant, A β -containing fibrin clots. Together with oligomeric A β , these clots trigger vessel constriction and cerebral amyloid angiopathy (CAA) with vessel occlusion and hemorrhages, leading to vascular and BBB dysfunction. As a consequence, brain blood flow, perfusion, and supply with oxygen (hypoxia) and nutrients decrease. In parenchymal tissue, hypoxia stimulates A β synthesis, leading to A β accumulation, which is further enhanced by BBB-impaired perivascular A β clearance. A β triggers neuronal damage and promotes tau pathologies. BBB dysfunction enables thrombin and fibrin(ogen) to migrate into parenchymal tissue and to activate glial cells. Inflammation and continued A β production are the results. Synapses and neurons die, and cognitive abilities are lost. DOACs block thrombin by inhibiting its activity or production—FXa inhibitors. The administration of DOACs may contribute to the preservation of vascular integrity and cerebral perfusion, thereby potentially mitigating vascular-induced neuronal and cognitive decline associated with Alzheimer's disease. A proposed framework for clinical investigation has been formulated, emphasizing the application of DOAC therapy in patients diagnosed with early-stage Alzheimer's disease who present a low risk of major hemorrhagic complications (Grossmann et al. 2023).

The use of DOACs versus vitamin K antagonists (VKAs) among patients with AF, VTE, and PE has shifted significantly in recent years (Yan et al. 2023). DOACs have become more prevalent in the treatment of AF compared to VKAs. Recent data indicates that approximately 47.9% of AF patients are treated with DOACs, while the use of warfarin has decreased to around 17.7% (Khairani et al. 2023). For VTE, including both DVT and PE, DOACs are increasingly favored due to their ease of use and safety profile. In some studies, about 11.5% of VTE patients were receiving DOAC therapy, while 88.5% were on warfarin, although this can vary by region and specific patient demographics (Fang et al. 2023). As a subset of VTE, the treatment

patterns for PE generally align with those for VTE overall, with a growing preference for DOACs over VKAs due to similar reasons (Fang et al. 2023). In all these mentioned pathological conditions, the goal of anticoagulant therapy is to influence the pathological formation of thrombus. The mechanisms of the drugs vary depending on which stage of the coagulation cascade they affect (Fig. 1).

At present, the DOACs available on the market comprise dabigatran, rivaroxaban, apixaban, edoxaban, and betrixaban. While ongoing research and development continue to explore novel anticoagulant therapies, these agents remain the most frequently utilized in clinical practice. The latest advancements and findings regarding their efficacy and safety will be closely reviewed (Colacci et al. 2020) (Table 1).

Figure 1. Coagulation cascade and anticoagulants (Anticoagulants—Heme—Medbullets Step 2/3).

Table 1. Mechanism of action, indications, and drug interactions of most common DOACs.

	Warfarin	Dabigatran	Rivaroxaban	Apixaban	Edoxaban	Betrixaban
Mechanism	Vit K antagonist (II, VII, IX, X)	Direct thrombin inhibitor	Direct Xa inhibitor	Direct Xa inhibitor	Direct Xa inhibitor	Direct Xa inhibitor
Indication	Cardioembolic stroke, VTE	Nonvalvular AF, VTE treatment	Nonvalvular AF, VTE treatment VTE prophylaxis (ortho) AF:	Nonvalvular AF, VTE treatment, VTE prophylaxis (ortho)	Nonvalvular AF, VTE treatment, VTE prophylaxis (ortho)	VTE treatment
Dose	Variable INR* goal is usually 2–3	Nonvalvular AF, VTE: 150 mg BID (CrCL > 30 ml/min) 75 mg BID (CrCL 15–30 mL/min) Non recommended CrCL < 15 mL/min	20 mg once daily with food 15 mg once daily (CrCL 15–50 mL/min) Ortho: 10 mg once daily VTE: 15 mg BID for 30 days; after that, 20 mg once daily	AF: 5 mg BID if ≥ 2 or following ≥ 80 years, ≤ 60 kg, Cl ≥ 1.5 mg/dl Orto: BID 2.5 mg VTE: 10 mg BID for 7 days; after, that 5 mg BID for 6 months	60 mg once daily or 30 mg once daily (CrCl 15–50 mL/min)	VTE: Oral: 160 mg as a single dose on day 1, followed by 80 mg once daily for 35 to 42 days VTE with CrCl Oral: 80 mg as a single dose on day 1, followed by 40 mg once daily for 35 to 42 days
Onset	48–120 h	1–2 h	2–4 h	3–4 h	1–2 h	3–4 h
Half-life	20–60 h	12–17 h	5–9 h	8–12 h	10–14 h	19–27 h
Drug interaction	↑ Warfarin effects: Herbals, amiodarone/dronedarone antifungals, antibiotics, HIV medication, phenytoin, acute ethanol ingestion; ↓ Warfarin effects: phenobarbital, carbamazepine, rifampin, chronic ethanol ingestion	↑ Dabigatran effects: dronedarone ketoconazole ↓ Dabigatran effects: rufampin	↑ Rivaroxaban effects: ketoconazole clarithromycin erythromycin fluconazole ritonavir ↓ Rivaroxaban effects: rufampin	↑ Apixaban effects: ketoconazole clarithromycin erythromycin amiodarone/dronedarone ↓ Apixaban effects: rufampin	↑ Edoxaban effects: ketoconazole clarithromycin cyclosporine amiodarone/dronedarone ↓ Edoxaban effects: rufampin	↑ Betrixaban effects: ketoconazole clarithromycin cyclosporine amiodarone/dronedarone ↓ Betrixaban effects: rufampin phenytoin carbamazepine
Contraindications	Child-Pugh C	CrCl ≤ 15 ml/min	CrCl ≤ 15 ml/min, Child-Pugh C	CrCl ≤ 15–25 ml/min, Child-Pugh C	CrCl > 95 ml/min (reduced efficacy)	

*INR – International normalized ratio.

Based on their mechanism of action, DOACs are classified as:

1. Direct thrombin inhibitors, with dabigatran as the sole representative (dabigatran etexilate) (Pradaxa®) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Chemical structure of dabigatran (CSID:187412, <https://www.chemspider.com/Chemical-Structure.187412.html>, accessed 6 May 2025, 18:57).

Dabigatran stands out as the only direct thrombin inhibitor and a pro-drug. By binding reversibly to the active site of thrombin, dabigatran attenuates thrombin activity and reduces fibrin formation. This mechanism effectively halts the final step in the coagulation cascade (dabigatran SmPC).

Dabigatran is primarily used to reduce the risk of stroke and systemic embolism in patients with non-valvular AF. It is also indicated for the treatment of DVT and PE in patients who have been treated with a parenteral anticoagulant for 5–10 days. Additionally, dabigatran is used to reduce the risk of recurrence of DVT and PE in patients who have been previously treated. Furthermore, it is indicated for the prophylaxis of DVT and PE following hip replacement surgery (dabigatran SmPC).

The most frequently discussed side effect of dabigatran, as highlighted in the registration summary, is bleeding, which is considered the most serious adverse effect. Major or severe bleeding can occur, potentially leading to disabling, life-threatening, or even fatal outcomes. Bleeding can manifest in various forms, such as gastrointestinal bleeding, intracranial hemorrhage, and bleeding from other sites. The risk of bleeding is higher in patients with certain risk factors, such as advanced age, renal impairment, and concomitant use of other medications that affect hemostasis. Dyspepsia is another common adverse effect, affecting up to 10% of users, and is primarily related to the mechanism of the drug rather than the dose. This includes symptoms such as acid or sour stomach, heartburn, and stomach discomfort. Taking dabigatran with meals can help reduce the frequency of this complication. Gastrointestinal issues such as nausea, diarrhea, and abdominal pain are also common but usually mild and may resolve over time. Taking the medication with meals can help reduce the frequency of this complication (dabigatran SmPC).

2. Factor Xa inhibitors—includes rivaroxaban, apixaban, edoxaban, and betrixaban.

Rivaroxaban (Xarelto®)

Figure 3. Chemical structure of rivaroxaban (CSID:8051086, <https://www.chemspider.com/Chemical-Structure.8051086.html>, accessed 6 May 2025, 18:47).

Rivaroxaban binds selectively to the active site of factor Xa, inhibiting both free and clot-bound factor Xa. This action interrupts both the intrinsic and extrinsic pathways of the coagulation cascade. It is administered with once-daily dosing. This dosing regimen significantly improves patient compliance (Fig. 3) (Elnaem et al. 2020). Clinical indications for rivaroxaban include stroke prevention in patients with non-valvular AF to reduce the risk of stroke and systemic embolism. It is also approved for treating DVT and PE, as well as reducing the risk of recurrence. Additionally, rivaroxaban is used for VTE prevention in patients undergoing knee or hip replacement surgery. Unique among DOACs, rivaroxaban is approved for reducing the risk of major cardiovascular events in patients with chronic CAD or PAD (rivaroxaban SmPC). Rivaroxaban is mostly administered once daily, which offers the convenience of simplified dosing and can improve patient compliance when it comes to prophylaxis, but it can also be used twice daily in rare cases in severe conditions as treatment. Dose depends on the condition and the kidney function of the patient.

Apixaban (Eliquis®)

Figure 4. Chemical structure of apixaban (CSID:8358471, <https://www.chemspider.com/Chemical-Structure.8358471.html>, accessed 6 May 2025, 18:45).

Apixaban is an oral, direct, and highly selective factor Xa inhibitor that targets both free and bound factor Xa, as well as prothrombinase, independent of antithrombin III. It is administered with twice-daily dosing due to its pharmacokinetic specifics (Fig. 4).

Clinical indications for apixaban include stroke prevention in patients with non-valvular AF to reduce the risk of stroke and systemic embolism. It is also approved for the treatment of DVT and PE. Additionally, apixaban is used for VTE prophylaxis in patients who have undergone hip or knee replacement surgery (Product information for Eliquis/Bristol-Myers Squibb Company, Princeton, NJ 08543, November 2019). Administered daily intake is twice, with variability of the dose depending on the condition, kidney function, and body weight of the subject.

Edoxaban (Savaysa® or Lixiana®)

Figure 5. Chemical structure of edoxaban (CSID:8456212, <https://www.chemspider.com/Chemical-Structure.8456212.html>, accessed 6 May 2025, 18:43).

Similar to apixaban and rivaroxaban, edoxaban is an oral, direct factor Xa inhibitor that selectively inhibits both free and clot-bound factor Xa, as well as prothrombinase activity (Fig. 5). This action interrupts both the intrinsic and extrinsic pathways of the coagulation cascade, preventing thrombin generation and thrombus formation. Edoxaban is administered once daily, which offers the convenience of simplified dosing and can improve patient compliance (Elnaem et al. 2020).

Edoxaban is indicated for stroke prevention in patients with non-valvular AF, reducing the risk of stroke and systemic embolism. It is also approved for the treatment of DVT and PE, as well as for the prevention of recurrent DVT and PE. Edoxaban is administered once daily. The decision of the dose depends on the condition and kidney function of the patient (edoxaban SmPC).

DOACs are characterized by their wider application targets and improved safety profile, which has led to increased interest in this group of cardiovascular agents. In this relation, a number of studies reported a markedly decreased incidence of composite dementia in anticoagulated patients with atrial fibrillation, with the highest benefit for direct oral anticoagulants. However, sub-analyses by differential dementia diagnosis are still scarce and inconclusive (Toribio-Fernandez et al. 2024).

The comparison of different DOACs suggests that factor Xa inhibitors, such as rivaroxaban, apixaban, and edoxaban, are particularly useful due to their efficacy and safety in various clinical settings. These medications

offer effective anticoagulation with the convenience of once-daily or twice-daily dosing, reducing the need for frequent monitoring.

Advantages and disadvantages in use of DOACs

DOACs have several advantages over traditional VKA antagonists. They have a more predictable effect due to their predictable pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics. This allows fixed dosing regimens without the need for routine monitoring (Eikelboom and Weitz 2010; Dunois 2021). Fixed doses provide consistent anticoagulation effects, reducing variability in patient response and assuring good compliance (Elnaem et al. 2020). Another positive aspect of the use of DOACs is the rapid onset of action (Kreutz 2014). This is particularly beneficial in acute settings where immediate anticoagulation is required. They also have a shorter half-life compared to VKAs, allowing for quicker reversal of anticoagulation if necessary (Shih and Crowther 2016).

Some recent investigations suggest that among AF patients, treatment with DOACs for a period of 10 years is associated with lower risk of all-cause dementia and vascular dementia compared to VKA treatment. This effect is not apparent in those treated for shorter durations. This finding requires confirmation in ongoing randomized controlled trials (Sagris et al. 2024).

While DOACs offer several advantages over traditional VKA antagonists, they also come with certain disadvantages.

One of the primary concerns is cost, as DOACs are generally more expensive than VKAs in the short-term perspective (Noviyani et al. 2022), which can be a barrier for some patients, especially those without adequate insurance coverage. In the long-term perspective, data concluded that DOACs are a cost-effective option for stroke prevention in elderly AF patients. Additionally, a study published in Clinical Drug Investigation compared the economic implications of DOACs and VKAs using real-world evidence from the Italian National Health System perspective. The study found that despite higher acquisition costs, DOACs led to overall cost savings due to reduced incidence of stroke, major bleeding, and other adverse events (Lorenzoni et al. 2021). Therefore, despite the overall favorable safety profile, bleeding risk remains a critical issue in the selection of the appropriate oral anticoagulant drug. Indeed, there are no head-to-head studies comparing the safety and efficacy of different DOACs, and bearing in mind the differences in clinical trial designs as well as the patient characteristics enrolled, definitive conclusions cannot be stated due to numerous biases (Lavalle et al. 2020). Available perioperative data are principally generated from RCT substudies, and considering the DOAC pharmacokinetic parameters (short time to peak effect and short half-life), periprocedural bridging is usually not required (Doherty et al. 2017). However, decisions in elective situations about stopping DOACs perioperatively should

be based on the thromboembolic risk of the patient as well as general characteristics, the bleeding risk of the invasive procedures, and the DOAC pharmacokinetics profile. Furthermore, coagulation monitoring might be useful in certain populations, considering the elevated interindividual variability of DOAC plasma concentrations (Doherty et al. 2017; Barnes and Moulard 2018).

Overall, DOACs are eliminated by the kidneys in different amounts, and alterations in hepatic function may deeply impact their metabolism (CYP enzymes) and elimination. As reported before dabigatran is the most renally eliminated (80%), followed by edoxaban (50%), rivaroxaban (35%), and apixaban (27%) (Stefel et al. 2018). Renal function evaluation and monitoring need to be performed before and during treatment with DOACs, and dosage corrections should be performed accordingly, preventing also subtherapeutic dosages (Yao et al. 2017). Indeed, an inappropriate DOAC dose, due to renal impairment, can increase the risk of bleeding or thrombosis, as reported in up to 32% of patients (Brophy and Human 2017; Sanghai et al. 2020; Dunois 2021).

teract with certain medications, such as strong inhibitors or inducers of P-glycoprotein and CYP3A4 (Vranckx et al. 2018; Khan et al. 2020; Dunois 2021; Park et al. 2022).

Despite these disadvantages, DOACs remain a valuable option for many patients, and their benefits often outweigh the risks. It is essential to evaluate each patient's individual circumstances and medical history when choosing the most appropriate anticoagulant therapy.

Biotransformation of DOACs

Being structurally related molecules, DOACs are more or less chemically similar. However, some structural differences lead to significant variations in their biotransformation, binding to plasma proteins, and elimination from the body. Based on these factors, the choice of DOAC is determined with a focus on patient specifics.

When it comes to medications, biotransformation and metabolism are synonymous. Biotransformation, or metabolism, occurs in three phases involving drug-metabolizing enzyme systems in the liver.

Figure 6. Metabolism of pesticides by human cytochrome P450 enzymes *in vitro* (Abass et al. 2012).

While DOACs have been shown to be effective and safe in clinical trials, there is still a lack of long-term data compared to VKAs, which have been used for decades. This lack of long-term data can be a concern for some healthcare providers and patients. Additionally, although DOACs have fewer interactions than VKAs, they can still in-

teract with certain medications, such as strong inhibitors or inducers of P-glycoprotein and CYP3A4 (Vranckx et al. 2018; Khan et al. 2020; Dunois 2021; Park et al. 2022).

Phase I: This phase involves chemical modifications such as oxidation, reduction, and hydrolysis. Enzymes like cytochrome P450 play a crucial role in these reactions, making the drug more water-soluble and preparing it for further modifications (Fig. 6) (Montellano 2015; Behrendorff 2021).

Phase II: In this phase, the drug or its metabolites from Phase I undergo conjugation reactions. This involves the addition of endogenous substances like glucuronic acid, sulfate, or glutathione, further increasing the drug's water solubility and facilitating its excretion (Talevi and Bellera 2021; Mohsin et al. 2024).

Phase III: This phase involves the transport of the drug and its metabolites out of the cells and into the bile or urine for elimination. Transport proteins such as P-glycoprotein are essential in this process (Talevi and Bellera 2021).

These phases ensure that drugs are effectively metabolized and eliminated from the body, maintaining their

therapeutic efficacy and minimizing potential toxicity. In addition to the crucial role of cytochrome P450 (CYP450) enzymes, P-glycoprotein (P-gp) also plays an important role in drug transport and metabolism. Also known as multi-drug resistance protein 1 (MDR1) or ATP-binding cassette sub-family B member 1 (ABCB1), P-gp is a vital protein involved in drug transport and metabolism. It functions as an ATP-dependent efflux pump, utilizing energy from ATP to transport various substances out of cells. P-glycoprotein is expressed in various tissues, including the intestines, liver, kidneys, and BBB, where it helps protect the body from potentially harmful substances by promoting their elimination (Finch and Pillans 2014; Yu et al. 2017).

General introduction of CYP P450

Oxidative reactions associated are always considered separately due to their extremely important role and the numerous reactions they participate in (Behrendorff 2021; Abdelmonem et al. 2024). Cytochrome P450 isoenzymes are catalytically and structurally similar but genetically distinct enzymes and are in the center of the process. They have different amino acid sequences, which result in varying substrate specificities. There are over 50 CYP450 enzymes, but the isoforms CYP1A2, CYP2A6, CYP2B6, CYP2C9, CYP2D6, CYP2E1, and CYP3A4 are particularly important. These isoforms are responsible for catalyzing the metabolism of more than 90% of drugs and xenobiotics in the human body (Lynch and Price 2007; Abdelmonem et al. 2024).

Way of biotransformation of DOACs

Dabigatran and betrixaban are both DOACs with unique metabolic pathways that are not primarily dependent on the liver (Fig. 7).

Dabigatran is administered as the prodrug dabigatran etexilate, which is rapidly converted to its active form, dabigatran, in the body. Dabigatran is not metabolized by cytochrome P450 enzymes and has minimal interactions with food and other drugs. Its elimination is predominantly through renal excretion, with approximately 80% of the drug being excreted unchanged in the urine (Gustafsson and Elg 2003; Antonijevic et al. 2017).

Betrixaban's minimal hepatic metabolism presents a significant advantage for patients with hepatic diseases. Given that less than 1% of the drug undergoes metabolism via the liver, the risk of accumulation and toxicity in individuals with impaired liver function is substantially reduced (Portola Pharma UK Limited 2018; Betrixaban SmPC, EMA). This characteristic enhances its safety profile compared to other anticoagulants that rely more heavily on hepatic metabolism. The principal metabolic transformation occurs through hydrolysis, yielding two major inactive metabolites, PRT062802 and PRT062803 (Hutchaleelaha

et al. 2012). These metabolites are further processed, with PRT062802 being the most prominent metabolite detected in human urine and feces. Additionally, two CYP-mediated metabolites, O-desmethyl betrixaban (PRT058326) and N-desmethyl betrixaban (PRT054156), are observed in plasma at trace levels (Hutchaleelaha et al. 2012).

Betrixaban's primary elimination through fecal excretion minimizes renal burden, making it a viable option for patients with concurrent liver and kidney impairments. The predominant route of elimination is fecal excretion, wherein approximately 85% of the administered dose is expelled in its unchanged form. The remaining portion is excreted via the renal pathway, primarily in the form of inactive metabolites (Hutchaleelaha et al. 2012).

Rivaroxaban undergoes metabolism primarily through the action of cytochrome P450 (CYP450) isoenzymes. The structural changes in rivaroxaban under the action of these enzymes involve various oxidative reactions (Fig. 8). The key CYP450 isoenzymes involved in the metabolism of rivaroxaban include CYP2J2, CYP3A4, CYP2D6, and CYP4F3. Among these, CYP2J2 plays a dominant role in the hydroxylation of rivaroxaban, introducing hydroxyl groups to the molecule. This hydroxylation process results in the formation of hydroxylated metabolites, which can have different pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties compared to the parent drug.

Additionally, CYP3A4, CYP2D6, and CYP4F3 also contribute to the metabolism of rivaroxaban, albeit to a lesser extent. These enzymes facilitate various oxidative reactions, including N-dealkylation, O-dealkylation, and S-oxidation, further modifying the structure of rivaroxaban and aiding in its elimination from the body (Lynch and Price 2007; Harder 2014; Zhao et al. 2021). These reactions result in the formation of inactive metabolites, which are then excreted from the body via biliary and renal routes. Approximately 36% of the administered dose is excreted unchanged in the urine, while the rest is excreted through the feces. This multi-pathway elimination helps to ensure that rivaroxaban is effectively cleared from the body, maintaining its therapeutic efficacy and minimizing potential toxicity (Mueck et al. 2014).

About 33% of apixaban is metabolized in the liver, where it undergoes oxidative reactions such as O-demethylation and hydroxylation (Fig. 9). The metabolism of apixaban involves several oxidative reactions, leading to the formation of various metabolites. The key CYP450 isoenzymes involved in the metabolism of apixaban include:

- CYP3A4/5: These isoenzymes play a dominant role in the oxidative metabolism of apixaban. They catalyze the formation of O-demethylated and hydroxylated metabolites, which are the primary metabolites of apixaban.
- CYP1A2: This isoenzyme contributes to a minor extent in the formation of O-demethylated metabolites (Wong et al. 2011).
- CYP2J2: This isoenzyme also plays a minor role in the metabolism of apixaban, contributing to the formation of hydroxylated metabolites (He et al. 2006).

Figure 7. Probable chemical metabolic transformations of betrixaban (Hutchaleelaha et al. 2012).

Figure 8. CYP-dependent oxidation of rivaroxaban to hydroxylated rivaroxaban (Zhao et al. 2022).

Phase II metabolism of apixaban mainly involves glucuronidation and sulfation. These metabolites are considered inactive, meaning they do not contribute to the anticoagulant effect of apixaban. The remaining portion of apixaban that is not metabolized in the liver is primarily excreted unchanged. Apixaban is eliminated through multiple pathways, including renal and intestinal excretion. Approximately 25%

of the administered dose is excreted unchanged in the urine, while the rest is excreted through the feces. This multi-pathway elimination helps to ensure that apixaban is effectively cleared from the body, maintaining its therapeutic efficacy and minimizing potential toxicity (He et al. 2006).

Edoxaban is metabolized in the liver, but to a relatively minor extent (Fig. 10). The primary metabolic pathways for

Figure 9. Biotransformation of apixaban (Wong et al. 2011).

edoxaban involve hydrolysis, glucuronidation, and minimal involvement of cytochrome P450 (CYP450) enzymes, particularly CYP3A4. Approximately 50% of edoxaban is cleared through non-renal pathways, which include liver metabolism and biliary secretion. The primary active metabolite of edoxaban is known as M-4. This metabolite is formed through the action of carboxylesterase-1 (CES1) and retains pharmacological activity (Parasrampur and Truitt 2016).

The presence of active metabolites like M-4 can influence the overall anticoagulant effect of edoxaban and may interfere with certain assays used to measure edoxaban concentrations. The active metabolite M-4 of edoxaban retains pharmacological activity and contributes to the overall anticoagulant effect of the drug. However, the extent of its contribution is generally considered to be minor compared to the parent compound. M-4 is formed through the action of carboxylesterase-1 (CES1) and is excreted in bile and urine.

In patients with impaired renal function or those taking certain medications, the plasma concentrations of M-4 can increase to clinically significant levels. This can potentially enhance the anticoagulant effect and increase the risk of bleeding (Lip and Agnelli 2014). Edoxaban is primarily excreted through two main pathways—renal and fecal excretion. Approximately 60% of edoxaban is excreted via feces, and around 35% is excreted via urine (Lip and Agnelli 2014). The drug undergoes minimal metabolism, with over 70% of an edoxaban dose being excreted unchanged. This dual pathway of elimination helps ensure that edoxaban is effectively cleared from the body, maintaining its therapeutic efficacy and minimizing potential toxicity (Lip and Agnelli 2014).

Influence of CYP inducers and inhibitors on the biotransformation of DOACs

The biotransformation of DOACs can be significantly influenced by the presence of CYP450 inducers and inhibitors. CYP450 inducers increase the activity of CYP450 enzymes, leading to enhanced metabolism of DOACs. This can result in lower plasma concentrations of the anticoagulant, potentially reducing its efficacy. Examples of CYP450 inducers include rifampin, carbamazepine, and St. John's Wort (Herink et al. 2019). In contrast, CYP450 inhibitors decrease the activity of CYP450 enzymes, leading to reduced metabolism of DOACs. This can result in higher plasma concentrations of the anticoagulant, potentially increasing the risk of bleeding. Examples of CYP450 inhibitors include ketoconazole, erythromycin, and grapefruit juice (Herink et al. 2019).

For example, the CYP3A4 inhibitor ketoconazole can increase the plasma concentration of betrixaban by reducing its metabolism. This can enhance the anticoagulant effect and increase the risk of bleeding. On the other hand, the CYP3A4 inducer rifampin can decrease the plasma concentration of betrixaban by increasing its metabolism. This can reduce the anticoagulant effect and increase the risk of thromboembolism. Understanding these interactions is crucial for optimizing therapy and minimizing potential adverse effects (Hutchaleelaha et al. 2012; Kryukov et al. 2018).

An important parameter also influencing the biotransformation of DOACs is their ability to bind with P-glycoprotein

Figure 10. Probable chemical metabolic transformations of edoxaban (Parasrampur and Truitt 2016).

as substrates of P-gp, an efflux transporter located in the gut mucosa. Thus, P-glycoprotein inhibitors and inducers affect their activity. Drugs that inhibit P-gp, such as amiodarone, can increase the plasma concentration of DOACs by reducing their efflux from cells, enhancing the anticoagulant effect and increasing the risk of bleeding. Conversely, drugs that induce P-gp, such as St. John's Wort, can decrease the plasma concentration of DOACs by increasing their efflux from cells, reducing the anticoagulant effect and increasing the risk of thromboembolism (Vazquez 2018; Harskamp et al. 2019; Herink et al. 2019; Li et al. 2020; Wiggins et al. 2020). For example, betrixaban is a substrate of P-gp, and the presence of drugs that inhibit P-gp, such as amiodarone, can increase the plasma concentration of betrixaban by reducing its efflux from cells. This can enhance the anticoagulant effect and increase the risk of bleeding. On the other hand, P-glycoprotein inducers, such as St. John's Wort, can decrease the plasma concentration of betrixaban by increasing its efflux from cells. This can reduce the anticoagulant effect and increase the risk of thromboembolism.

Understanding these interactions is crucial for optimizing anticoagulant therapy and minimizing potential adverse effects.

Conclusion

Neurodegenerative disorders and cardiovascular disease (CVD) are strongly associated, both being multifactorial

disorders with long asymptomatic phases and similar risk factors. Worldwide, around 55 million people have dementia. Despite the expectation of an overall increase in the number of people affected by dementia, closely related to population aging, some epidemiological studies point towards a decline in incidence due to better management of CVRFs.

The advent of non-vitamin K antagonists, also known as DOACs, has provided an important alternative, and they are now recommended as preferred therapy for CVD whenever possible. Despite some disadvantages, DOACs remain a valuable option for many patients, and their benefits often outweigh the risks. Still, it remains essential to evaluate each patient's individual circumstances and medical history when choosing the most appropriate anticoagulant therapy.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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